

Fixed Point Results in Neutrosophic b- Metric Like Spaces

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Abstract: In this manuscript we introduce the idea of Neutrosophic b-metric like spaces along with numerous significant illustrations. Moreover, we present numerous fixed point results in Neutrosophic b-metric like space and we gave some examples to support our main results.

Keywords: b-metric like spaces; Neutrosophic b-metric like spaces; Fixed point; Contractive map; Unique solution.

1. Introduction

Zadeh [20], laid the foundation for fuzzy mathematics in 1965. Kramosil and Michalek[11] initially brought up the idea of fuzzy metric space and then refitted by George and Veeramani[4]. Harandi [5] imported the perception of metric-like spaces, which nicely broden the concept of metric spaces. *b*-Metric Like Spaces [*bMLS*] were first discussed by Alghamdiet al.[2] using the idea of metric like spaces. In this manner, Fuzzy Metric Like Space [*FMLS*] were developed by Shukla and Abbas [15] they also developed the concept of metric like space. Park [13] proposed the idea of intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces. Konwar [10] developed the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy *b*-metric space . We see [1, 6, 12, 19, 16, 17] for certain required definitions. In the framework of *b*-metric spaces, Delfani et al. [3] demonstrated several fixed point results. In 1998, Smarandache[18] developed the ideas of neutrosophic logic and Neutrosophic Set [*NS*]. Kirisci and Simsek[9] founded the concept of Neutrosophic Metric Spaces [*NMS*] which address membership, non-membership and neutralness.

We introduce the notion of Neutrosophic *b*-Metric Spaces [*NbMS*] in order to generalise the notion of *NbMS* and demonstrate several fixed point findings in this framework. We also furnish this work with examples.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [2] A *bMLS* on a set $\mathfrak{S} \neq \emptyset$ is a function $\varphi : \mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ such that for all $\hbar, q, r \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $b \geq 1$, if it enjoys the conditions listed below :

1. If $\varphi(\hbar, q) = 0$, then $\hbar = q$;
2. $\varphi(\hbar, q) = \varphi(q, \hbar)$;
3. $\varphi(\hbar, q) \leq b[\varphi(\hbar, r) + \varphi(r, q)]$.

The pair (\mathfrak{S}, φ) is said to be *bMLS*.

Example 2.2.[2] Let $\mathfrak{S} = [0, \infty)$. Define $\varphi : \mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ by $\varphi(\hbar, q) = (\hbar + q)^2$. Then (\mathfrak{S}, φ) is a *bMLS* with $b = 1$.

Definition 2.3. [5] A 3-tuple $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, *)$ is named to be a *FMLS* if $\mathfrak{S} \neq \emptyset$ is a random set, $*$ is a *CTN* and \mathfrak{A} is a *FS* on $\mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S} \times (0, \infty)$ such that for all $\hbar, q, r \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta, \omega > 0$,

- FL1). $\mathfrak{A}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) > 0$;
- FL2). If $\mathfrak{A}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1$, then $\hbar = q$;
- FL3). $\mathfrak{A}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}(q, \hbar, \vartheta)$;
- FL4). $\mathfrak{A}(\hbar, r, \vartheta + \omega) \geq \mathfrak{A}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) * \mathfrak{A}(q, r, \omega)$;
- FL5). $\mathfrak{A}(\hbar, q, \cdot): (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.

Example 2.4.[15] Let $\mathfrak{S} = \mathbb{R}^+, \rho \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $m > 0$. Define *CTN* by $\hbar * q = \hbar q$ and \mathfrak{A} by $\mathfrak{A}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \frac{\rho^\vartheta}{\rho^\vartheta + m(\max\{\hbar, q\})}$ for all $\hbar, q \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, *)$ is an *FMLS*.

Definition 2.5. Let $\mathfrak{S} \neq \emptyset$. For a sextuple $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}, *, \diamond)$, where $*$ is a *CTN*, \diamond is a *CTCN*, $b \geq 1$ and $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}$ are *FS* on $\mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S} \times (0, \infty)$, if $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}, *, \diamond)$ satisfies the following, for all $\hbar, q \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $\vartheta, \omega > 0$,

1. $0 \leq \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) \leq 1; 0 \leq \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) \leq 1; 0 \leq \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) \leq 1$;
2. $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) + \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) + \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) \leq 3$;
3. $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1 \Leftrightarrow \hbar = q$;
4. $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(q, \hbar, \vartheta)$;
5. $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, r, b(\vartheta + \omega)) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) * \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(q, r, \omega)$;
6. $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is neutrosophic continuous;
7. $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1$;
8. $\mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \hbar = q$;
9. $\mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(q, \hbar, \vartheta)$;
10. $\mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, r, b(\vartheta + \omega)) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(q, r, \omega)$;
11. $\mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is neutrosophic continuous;
12. $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0$;
13. $\mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \hbar = q$;
14. $\mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(q, \hbar, \vartheta)$;
15. $\mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, r, b(\vartheta + \omega)) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(q, r, \omega)$;
16. $\mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is neutrosophic continuous;
17. $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0$;
18. $\vartheta < 0$ then $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1$.

Then $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is called an *NbMLS*.

Remark 2.6. In the above definition, assume that a set \mathfrak{S} is a *NbMLS* with a *CTN*($*$) and *CTCN*(\diamond). Then the *NbMLS* \mathfrak{S} does not satisfy (3), (8) and (13) of *NbMS*, that is, the self-distance may not be equal to 1 and 0, i.e., $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta) \neq 1, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta) \neq 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta) \neq 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$ or may be for all $\vartheta \in \mathfrak{S}$. But all other conditions are the same.

Example 2.7. Let $\mathfrak{S} = (0, \infty)$. Define a *CTN* by $u * v = uv$ and a *CTCN* by $u \diamond v = \max\{u, v\}$ and also define $\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}$ by

$$\mathfrak{A}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \left[e^{\frac{(\hbar+q)^2}{\vartheta}} \right]^{-1}, \mathfrak{B}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1 - \left[e^{\frac{(\hbar+q)^2}{\vartheta}} \right]^{-1} \text{ and } \mathfrak{C}_{b\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = \left[e^{\frac{(\hbar+q)^2}{\vartheta}} \right] - 1$$

for all $\hbar, q \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0$. Then it is an *NbMLS*. But it is not an *NbMS*.

Remark 2.8 The above example shows that *NbMLS* need not be an *NbMS*. Also every *NbMS* must be an *NbMLS*.

The following example shows that *NbMLS* need not be continuous.

Example 2.9 Let $\mathfrak{S} = [0, \infty)$, $\mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = e^{-\frac{\varphi(\hbar+q)}{\vartheta}}$, $\mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1 - \left(e^{-\frac{\varphi(\hbar+q)}{\vartheta}} \right)$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = e^{\frac{\varphi(\hbar+q)}{\vartheta}} - 1$ for all $\hbar, q \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0$ and $\varphi(\hbar, q) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \hbar = q \\ 2(\hbar + q)^2, & \text{if } \hbar, q \in [0,1] \\ \frac{1}{2}(\hbar + q)^2, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Define a CTN by $u * v = uv$ and a CTCN by $u \diamond v = \max\{u, v\}$. Then $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is a NbMLS with a coefficient $b=4$. To illustrate the discontinuity, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell} \left(0, \frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta \right) &= \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} e^{-2(1-\frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}})^2} = e^{-2} = \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(0,1, \vartheta) \\ \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell} \left(0, \frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta \right) &= 1 - \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} e^{-2(1-\frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}})^2} = 1 - e^{-2} = \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(0,1, \vartheta) \text{ and} \\ \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell} \left(0, \frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta \right) &= \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} e^{2(1-\frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}})^2} - 1 = e^2 - 1 = \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(0,1, \vartheta) \end{aligned}$$

Since,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell} \left(1, 1 - \frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta \right) &= \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} e^{-2(2-\frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}})^2} = e^{-8} \neq 1 = \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(1,1, \vartheta) \\ \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell} \left(1, 1 - \frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta \right) &= 1 - \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} e^{-2(2-\frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}})^2} = 1 - e^{-8} \neq 0 = \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(1,1, \vartheta) \\ \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell} \left(1, 1 - \frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta \right) &= \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} e^{2(2-\frac{1}{\mathfrak{n}})^2} - 1 = e^8 - 1 \neq 0 = \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(0,1, \vartheta) \end{aligned}$$

$\mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta)$, $\mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta)$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta)$ are not continuous.

Definition 2.10. A sequence $\{\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}\}$ in an NbMLS $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is converge to $\hbar \in \mathfrak{S}$ if $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta)$, $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta)$ and $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta)$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

Definition 2.11. A sequence $\{\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}\}$ in an NbMLS $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is named to be a Cauchy sequence if $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta)$, $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta)$ and $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta)$ exist and are finite for all $\vartheta \geq 0, p \geq 1$.

Definition 2.12. An NbMLS $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is named to be complete if every Cauchy sequence $\{\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}\}$ in \mathfrak{S} tends to some $\hbar \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta)$
 $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta)$ and
 $\lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, \hbar, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta)$ for all $\vartheta \geq 0, p \geq 1$.

3. Main Results.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete NbMLS such that $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 1, \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\hbar, q \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0$ and $J: \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}$ be a mapping satisfying the conditions $\mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(J\hbar, Jq, \tau\vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta)$, $\mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(J\hbar, Jq, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta)$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(J\hbar, Jq, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\hbar, q, \vartheta)$ (3.1.1) for all $\hbar, q \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0, \tau \in (0,1)$. Then \mathfrak{S} has a unique fixed point $\mathfrak{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $\mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

Proof: Let $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{b,\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{b,\ell}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete NbMLS. For a given element $\hbar_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$, define a sequence $\{\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}\}$ in \mathfrak{S} by

$$\hbar_1 = J\hbar_0, \hbar_2 = J^2\hbar = J\hbar_1, \dots, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}} = J^{\mathfrak{n}}\hbar_0 = J\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}-1} \text{ for each } \mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$$

If $\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}} = \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}-1}$ for some $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}$ is a fixed point of J . We consider that $\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}} \neq \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}-1}$ for each $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$. For $\vartheta > 0$ and $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$, we get from (3.1.1) that

$$\mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \tau\vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(J\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, J\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \tau\vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{b,\ell}(\hbar_{\mathfrak{n}}, \hbar_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta)$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \tau\vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \vartheta) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \tau\vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \vartheta)$$

for all $\check{n} \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\vartheta > 0$. Thus, by using the above expression we can deduce that

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \tau\vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \tau\vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \vartheta) \tag{3.1.2}$$

$$= \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-2}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-2}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau}\right) \geq \dots \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_1, \check{h}_0, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau^{\check{n}}}\right)$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \tau\vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \vartheta) \tag{3.1.3}$$

$$= \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-2}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-2}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau}\right) \leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_1, \check{h}_0, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau^{\check{n}}}\right) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}}, \tau\vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \vartheta) \tag{3.1.4}$$

$$= \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}-2}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}-1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}-2}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau}\right) \leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_1, \check{h}_0, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau^{\check{n}}}\right)$$

foreach $\check{n} \in \mathbb{N}, p \geq 1$ and $\vartheta > 0$. Thus we have

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right)$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right)$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right)$$

Continuing in this way, we get

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) * \dots * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+p-1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right)$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+p-1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+p-1}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right)$$

Using (3.1.2), (3.1.3) and (3.1.4) in the above inequality, we have

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b\tau^{\check{n}}}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2\tau^{\check{n}+1}}\right) * \dots * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}\tau^{\check{n}+p-1}}\right) \tag{3.1.5}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b\tau^{\check{n}}}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2\tau^{\check{n}+1}}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}\tau^{\check{n}+p-1}}\right) \tag{3.1.6}$$

and

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b\tau^{\check{n}}}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2\tau^{\check{n}+1}}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_0, \check{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}\tau^{\check{n}+p-1}}\right) \tag{3.1.7}$$

Here b is a random positive integer.

We know that $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}, q, \vartheta) = 1, \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}, q, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}, q, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\check{h}, q \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $\vartheta > 0, \tau \in (0,1)$. It follows from (3.1.5), (3.1.6) and (3.1.7) that for all $\vartheta > 0, p \geq 1$

$$\lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) = 1 * 1 * \dots * 1 = 1,$$

$$\lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) = 0 \diamond 0 \diamond \dots \diamond 0 = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) = 0 \diamond 0 \diamond \dots \diamond 0 = 0$$

Hence $\{\check{h}_{\check{n}}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. The completeness of the $NbMLS (\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}, *, \diamond)$ ensures that there exists $\check{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that for all $\vartheta > 0, p \geq 1$

$$\lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{d}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{d}, \check{d}, \vartheta) = 1 \tag{3.1.8}$$

$$\lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{d}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{d}, \check{d}, \vartheta) = 0 \tag{3.1.9}$$

$$\lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{d}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\check{n} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+p}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{d}, \check{d}, \vartheta) = 0. \tag{3.1.10}$$

Now, we show that $\check{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ is a fixed point of \mathcal{J} . We have

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}(\check{d}, \mathcal{J}\check{d}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{d}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \mathcal{J}\check{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right)$$

$$= \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{d}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\mathcal{J}\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \mathcal{J}\check{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right)$$

$$\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{d}, \check{h}_{\check{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{L}}\left(\check{h}_{\check{n}}, \check{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b\tau}\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, J\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &= \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, J\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \text{ and} \\ &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b\tau}\right) \\ \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, J\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &= \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, J\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b\tau}\right) \end{aligned}$$

for each $\vartheta > 0$. Taking the limit as $\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow +\infty$, and by (3.1.8),(3.1.9) and (3.1.10), we get $\mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1 * 1 = 1$ and $\mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0 \diamond 0 = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0 \diamond 0 = 0$. Therefore, \mathfrak{d} is a fixed point of J and $\mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$. Now, we examine the uniqueness of fixed point. For this, assume that \mathfrak{h} and \mathfrak{d} are two distinct fixed points of J . Then by (3.1.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) &= \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(J\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau}\right) \\ \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) &= \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(J\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau}\right) \text{ and} \\ \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) &= \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(J\mathfrak{d}, J\mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau}\right) \end{aligned}$$

for all $\vartheta > 0$. Thus we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) &\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau^{\mathfrak{n}}}\right) \text{ for all } \mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N} \\ \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau^{\mathfrak{n}}}\right) \text{ and } \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \frac{\vartheta}{\tau^{\mathfrak{n}}}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Letting the limit as $\mathfrak{n} \rightarrow +\infty$ and using $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = 1, \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = 0$ we get $\mathfrak{d} = \mathfrak{h}$. Thus the fixed point is unique.

Example 3.2. Let $\mathfrak{S} = [0,1]$ and the CTN and CTCN respectively defined by $u * v = uv$ and $u \diamond v = \max\{u, v\}$. Also, $\mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}$ are defined by $u * v = \min\{u, v\}$ and $u \diamond v = \max\{u, v\}$.

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = e^{-\frac{(\mathfrak{h}+\mathfrak{q})^2}{\vartheta}}, \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = 1 - e^{-\frac{(\mathfrak{h}+\mathfrak{q})^2}{\vartheta}} \text{ and } \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = e^{\frac{(\mathfrak{h}+\mathfrak{q})^2}{\vartheta}} - 1 \text{ for all } \mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q} \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0.$$

Then $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is a complete NMLS. Define $J: \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}$ by $J\mathfrak{h} = \begin{cases} 0, & \mathfrak{h} \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \\ \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{6}, & \mathfrak{h} \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \end{cases}$

Then

$$\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} e^{-\frac{(\mathfrak{h}+\mathfrak{q})^2}{\vartheta}} = 1, \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{(\mathfrak{h}+\mathfrak{q})^2}{\vartheta}}\right) = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow \infty} \left(e^{\frac{(\mathfrak{h}+\mathfrak{q})^2}{\vartheta}} - 1\right) = 0$$

For $\tau \in \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right)$, we have four cases:

Case 1) If $\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q} \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right]$, then $J\mathfrak{h} = J\mathfrak{q} = 0$.

Case 2) If $\mathfrak{h} \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right]$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$, then $J\mathfrak{h} = 0$ and $J\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{6}$.

Case 3) If $\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q} \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$, then $J\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{6}$ and $J\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{6}$.

Case 4) If $\mathfrak{h} \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right]$, then $J\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{6}$ and $J\mathfrak{q} = 0$.

From all four cases, we obtain that

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}, J\mathfrak{q}, \tau\vartheta) \geq \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta), \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}, J\mathfrak{q}, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \text{ and } \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}, J\mathfrak{q}, \tau\vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta).$$

Thus all the requirements of Theorem (3.1) are met and 0 is the unique fixed point of J . Also,

$$\mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{A}_{\beta\ell}(0, 0, \vartheta) = e^0 = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{\beta\ell}(0, 0, \vartheta) = 1 - e^0 = 0$$

and $\mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{\beta\ell}(0, 0, \vartheta) = e^0 - 1 = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

Definition 3.3. Let $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, *, \diamond)$ be an *NbMLS*. A mapping $J : \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}$ is named to be *NbML* contractive if there exists $\rho \in (0,1)$ such that

$$\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}, J\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)} - 1 \leq \rho \left[\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)} - 1 \right], \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}, J\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \text{ and } \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}, J\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \quad (I)$$

for all $\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q} \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $\vartheta > 0$. Here ρ is called the *NbML* contractive constant of J .

Theorem 3.4. Let $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete *NbMLS* and $J : \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}$ be a *NbML* contractive mapping with an *NbML* contractive constant ρ . Then J has a unique fixed point $\mathfrak{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

Proof: Let $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete *NbMLS*. For a given element $\mathfrak{p}_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$, define a sequence $\{\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}\}$ in \mathfrak{S} by

$$\mathfrak{h}_1 = J\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_2 = J^2\mathfrak{h}_0 = J\mathfrak{h}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}} = J^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{h}_0 = J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1} \text{ for all } \mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$$

If $\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}} = \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}$ for some $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}$ is a fixed point of J . We assume that $\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}} \neq \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}$ for all $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$. For $\vartheta > 0$ and $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$, we get from (I) that

$$\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta)} - 1 = \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta)} - 1 \leq \rho \left[\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta)} - 1 \right]$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta)} &\leq \frac{\rho}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta)} + (1 - \rho) \\ &= \frac{\rho}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-2}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta)} + (1 - \rho) \leq \frac{\rho^2}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-2}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta)} + \rho(1 - \rho) + (1 - \rho) \end{aligned}$$

for all $\vartheta > 0$. Continuing in this way, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta)} &\leq \frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{n}}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \vartheta)} + \rho^{\mathfrak{n}-1}(1 - \rho) + \rho^{\mathfrak{n}-2}(1 - \rho) + \dots + \rho(1 - \rho) + (1 - \rho) \\ &\leq \frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{n}}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \vartheta)} + (\rho^{\mathfrak{n}-1} + \rho^{\mathfrak{n}-2} + \dots + 1)(1 - \rho) \\ &\leq \frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{n}}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \vartheta)} + (1 - \rho^{\mathfrak{n}}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\frac{1}{\frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{n}}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \vartheta)} + (1 - \rho^{\mathfrak{n}})} \leq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta)$ for all $\vartheta > 0, \mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$ (3.4.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta) &= \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta) = \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-2}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta) \\ &\leq \rho^2 \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-2}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta) \leq \dots \leq \rho^{\mathfrak{n}} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \vartheta) \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.2)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta) &= \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \vartheta) = \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-2}, J\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta) \\ &\leq \rho^2 \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-2}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}-1}, \vartheta) \leq \dots \leq \rho^{\mathfrak{n}} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \vartheta). \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.3)$$

Now, for $p \geq 1$ and $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \vartheta) &\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+2}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this way, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta) &\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) * \dots * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p-1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right) \\ \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+2}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this way, we get

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p-1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{n}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+2}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this way, we get

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+2}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p-1}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right)$$

Using (3.4.1), (3.4.2) and (3.4.3) in the above inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) &\geq \frac{1}{\frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{ii}}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b})} + (1 - \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}})} * \frac{1}{\frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+1}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2})} + (1 - \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+1})} * \dots * \frac{1}{\frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+p-1}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}})} + (1 - \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+p-1})} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{ii}}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b})} + 1} * \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}) + 1} * \dots * \frac{\rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+p-1}}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}) + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+1} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+p-1} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) \leq \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b}\right) \diamond \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+1} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^2}\right) \diamond \dots \diamond \rho^{\mathfrak{ii}+p-1} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_0, \mathfrak{h}_1, \frac{\vartheta}{b^{p-1}}\right)$$

Where b is a random positive integer and $\rho \in (0, 1)$. So we deduce from the above expression that $\{\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, *, \diamond)$. By the completeness of $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, *, \diamond)$, there is $\mathfrak{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that

$$\lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1 \tag{3.4.4}$$

$$\lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0 \tag{3.4.5}$$

$$\lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = \lim_{\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+p}, \vartheta) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0 \tag{3.4.6}$$

for all $\vartheta > 0, p \geq 1$.

We now establish that \mathfrak{d} is a fixed point for \mathcal{J} . We determine this from (I) that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta)} - 1 &\leq \rho \left[\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta)} - 1 \right] = \frac{\rho}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta)} - \rho, \\ \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta)} + 1 - \rho &\leq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta). \end{aligned}$$

Utilize the above inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) &\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &= \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) * \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) * \frac{1}{\frac{\rho}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b})} + 1 - \rho} \\ \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) = \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) &\leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) = \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}+1}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \diamond \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}\left(\mathfrak{h}_{\mathfrak{ii}}, \mathfrak{d}, \frac{\vartheta}{2b}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Letting the limit as $\mathfrak{ii} \rightarrow \infty$ and applying (3.4.4), (3.4.5) and (3.4.6) in the above expression, we obtain that $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$, that is, $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d} = \mathfrak{d}$. Therefore, \mathfrak{d} is a fixed point of \mathcal{J} and $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

Now we demonstrate the uniqueness of the fixed point \mathfrak{d} of \mathcal{J} . Let \mathfrak{h} be a fixed point of \mathcal{J} different from \mathfrak{d} such that $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \neq 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \neq 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \neq 0$ for some $\vartheta > 0$. It follows from (3.4.1) that

$$\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta)} - 1 = \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}, \vartheta)} - 1 \leq \rho \left[\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta)} - 1 \right] < \frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta)} - 1$$

$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) < \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta)$ and

$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) = \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) < \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta)$ this is not possible.

\therefore we have $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{h}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$, and hence $\mathfrak{d} = \mathfrak{h}$.

Corollary 3.5. Let $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete NbMLS and $\mathcal{J}: \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}$ be a mapping satisfying $\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{h}, \mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)} - 1 \leq \rho \left[\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)} - 1 \right], \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{h}, \mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{h}, \mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)$ for some $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathbb{N}$ and all $\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q} \in \mathfrak{S}, \vartheta > 0, 0 < \rho < 1$. Then \mathcal{J} has a unique fixed point $\mathfrak{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ moreover $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

Proof: Assume that $\mathfrak{d} \in \mathfrak{S}$ is the unique fixed point of $\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}$ as determined by Theorem (3.4) and $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 1, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{d}, \mathfrak{d}, \vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$. So \mathfrak{d} is another fixed point of $\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}$ as $\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}) = \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d}$ and by Theorem(3.4), $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{d} = \mathfrak{d}$ and so \mathfrak{d} is the unique fixed point, since the unique fixed point of \mathcal{J} is also the unique fixed point of $\mathcal{J}^{\mathfrak{n}}$.

Example 3.6. Let $\mathfrak{S} = [0,1]$ and the CTN and CTCN respectively defined by $u * v = uv$ and $u \diamond v = \max\{u, v\}$. Consider $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}$ by $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = e^{-\frac{(\max\{\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}\})^2}{\vartheta}}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = 1 - e^{-\frac{(\max\{\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}\})^2}{\vartheta}}$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) = e^{\frac{(\max\{\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}\})^2}{\vartheta}} - 1$ for all $\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q} \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $\vartheta > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}, *, \diamond)$ is a complete NbMLS.

$$\text{Define } \mathcal{J}: \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S} \text{ as } \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \begin{cases} 0, & \mathfrak{h} = \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{2}, & \mathfrak{h} \in [0, \frac{1}{2}) \\ \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{4}, & \mathfrak{h} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1] \end{cases}$$

Then we have eight cases:

Case (i) If $\mathfrak{h} = \mathfrak{q} = \frac{1}{2}$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = 0$.

Case (ii) If $\mathfrak{h} = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$ then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = 0$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{2}$.

Case (iii) If $\mathfrak{h} = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = 0$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{4}$.

Case (iv) If $\mathfrak{h} \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{2}$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{4}$.

Case (v) If $\mathfrak{h} \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{2}$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{2}$.

Case (vi) If $\mathfrak{h} \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\mathfrak{q} = \frac{1}{2}$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{2}$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = 0$.

Case (vii) If $\mathfrak{h} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ and $\mathfrak{q} = \frac{1}{2}$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{4}$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = 0$.

Case (viii) If $\mathfrak{h} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ and $\mathfrak{q} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, then $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h} = \frac{\mathfrak{h}}{4}$ and $\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q} = \frac{\mathfrak{q}}{4}$.

NbML contraction is satisfied in all of the above cases:

$$\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)} - 1 \leq \rho \left[\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)} - 1 \right],$$

$\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)$ and

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathcal{J}\mathfrak{h}, \mathcal{J}\mathfrak{q}, \vartheta) \leq \rho \mathfrak{C}_{\mathcal{B}\ell}(\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{q}, \vartheta)$$

with the NbML contractive constant $\rho \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$.

Hence \mathcal{J} is an NbML contractive mapping with $\rho \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$.

All the requirements of Theorem (3.1) have been met.

Moreover, 0 is the unique fixed point of T and $\mathfrak{A}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(0,0,\vartheta) = 1$, $\mathfrak{B}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(0,0,\vartheta) = 0$ and $\mathfrak{C}_{\mathfrak{b},\ell}(0,0,\vartheta) = 0$ for all $\vartheta > 0$.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we develop *NbMLS* and demonstrate the fixed point theorem in order to demonstrate the unique fixed point in this space. This work is the extended form of fuzzy *b*-metric like space [6]. We hope that the result proved in this paper will form new connection for those who are working in the *NbMLS* space and this work opens a new path for researchers in the concerned field.

References

1. C. Alaca, D. Turkoglu and C. Yildiz, Fixed points in intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces, *Chaos Solitons Fractals* 29(2006),1073 – 1078
2. M.A. Alghamdi, N. Hussain and P. Salimi, Fixed point and coupled fixed point theorems in b-metric-like spaces, *J. Inequal. Appl.* 2013 (2013), Paper No. 402.
3. M. Delfani, A. Farajzadeh and C.F. Wen, Some fixed point theorems of generalized F_t -contraction mappings in b-metric spaces, *J. Nonlinear Var. Anal.* 5 (2021), 615-625.
4. A. George and P. Veeramani, On some results of analysis for fuzzy metric spaces, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 90 (1997), 365-368.
5. A. Harandi, Metric-like spaces, partial metric spaces and fixed point, *Fixed Point Theory Appl.* 2012 (2012), Paper No. 204
6. K. Javed, F. Uddin, H. Aydi, M. Arshad, U. Ishtiaq and H. Alsamir, On fuzzy b-metric-like spaces, *J. Funct. Spaces* 2021 (2021), Article ID 6615976.
7. Jeyaraman. M, Sowndrarajan. S. Some common fixed point theorems for $(\varphi - \psi)$ -weak contraction on intuitionistic Generalized fuzzy cone metric spaces. *Malaya journal mathematic.* 2019,1, 154-159.
8. Jeyaraman. M, Suganthi. M, Sowndrarajan. S. Fixed point results in non-Archimedean generalized intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces. *Notes on intuitionistics fuzzy sets*, 2019, 25, 45-58.
9. M. Kirişci, N. Simsek, Neutrosophic metric spaces, *Math. Sci.*, 14(2020), 241–248.
10. N. Konwar, Extension of fixed results in intuitionistic fuzzy b metric spaces, *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 39 (2020), 7831 – 7841.
11. I. Kramosil and J. Michleek, Fuzzy metric and statistical metric spaces, *Kybernetika* 11 (1975), 336-344.
12. A. Mohamad, Fixed-point theorems in intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces, *Chaos Solitons Fractals* 34 (2007), 16891695.
13. J.H. Park, Intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces, *Chaos Solitons Fractals* 22 (2004), 1039-1046.
14. B. Schweizer and A. Sklar, Statistical metric spaces, *Pacific J. Math.* 10 (1960), 14-34.
15. S. Shukla and M. Abbas, Fixed point results in fuzzy metric-like spaces, *Iran. J. Fuzzy Syst.* 11 (2014) no. 5, 81-92.
16. S. Shukla, D. Gopal and A.-F. Roldán-López-de-Hierro, Some fixed point theorems in 1-M-complete fuzzy metriclike spaces, *Int. J. Gen. Syst.* 45 (2016), 815-829.
17. W. Sintunavarat and P. Kumam, Fixed theorems for a generalized intuitionistic fuzzy contraction in intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces, *Thai J. Math.* 10 (2012), 123-135.
18. F.Smarandache, *Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic probability, set and logic*, Rehoboth: American Research Press, 1998.
19. M. Rafi and M.S.M. Noorani, Fixed theorems on intuitionistic fuzzy metric space, *Iran. J. Fuzzy Syst.* 3 (2006), 23-29.
20. L.A. Zadeh, Fuzzy sets, *Inform. Control* 3 (1965), 338-353.

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